

Topological superconductivity in superconducting chiral topological semimetals with parallel spin-momentum locking

Yingyi Huang^{1,2}

¹*School of Physics and Optoelectronic Engineering,
Guangdong University of Technology, Guangzhou 510006, China*

²*Guangdong Provincial Key Laboratory of Sensing Physics and System Integration Applications,
Guangdong University of Technology, Guangzhou, 510006, China*

(Dated: August 12, 2025)

In contrast to conventional Weyl semimetals in achiral crystals, chiral topological semimetals in chiral crystals exhibit Weyl nodes at time-reversal-invariant momenta. A Fermi surface spin texture with parallel spin-momentum locking in these material has been observed by a recent experiment [Nat. Comm. 15,3720(2024)]. We find that the Weyl nodes location and the Fermi surface spin texture lead to gapped zero-momenta intranode superconductivity (SC), which is absent in achiral Weyl semimetals. Through self-consistent mean-field calculations, we find that a cubic lattice system in general favors a mixture of spin-singlet s_{\pm} and $d+id$ -wave pairings. In the presence of only the s_{\pm} -wave pairing, we identify a first-order time-reversal invariant topological SC phase. Notably, an SC phase with two Majorana cones for opened Fermi surfaces is energetically favorable. In addition, a second-order topological superconductor with chiral Majorana states can be realized in the presence of a mixture of s_{\pm} - and $d+id$ -wave pairing. We show that chiral topological semimetals in cubic lattice are fascinating platforms for exploring intrinsic unconventional superconductivity and topological superconductivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Topological superconductors (TSCs) hosting Majorana zero modes have been actively pursued for its important role in fault-tolerant quantum computation [1–7]. The higher-order counterpart of TSC, which manifests as localized modes at $(d-m)$ -dimensional boundaries in a d -dimensional material is also an area of intense investigation [8–26]. However, only a limited number of realistic models have been proposed in intrinsic materials. Very recently, superconductivity have been observed in chiral topological semimetals [27, 28], a unique class of Weyl semimetals in nonmagnetic chiral crystals. These materials have been considered ideal candidates for conventional TSC [29–32]. However, the study of higher-order TSC in chiral topological semimetal is still lacking.

Chiral topological semimetals, realized in crystals lacking chirality-inverting symmetries, have attracted a lot of attention for their host of topological nontrivial fermions [33–39]. These topological fermions, including Kramers-Weyl fermion or multifold fermion, are located at time-reversal invariant momenta (TRIM), i.e., $\mathbf{k}_0 = -\mathbf{k}_0 + \mathbf{G}$, where \mathbf{G} is a reciprocal lattice vector [40–42]. This contrasts with Weyl fermions in achiral crystals (which posses mirror or roto-inversion symmetries), where the nodes are located away from TRIM \mathbf{k}_0 . For instance, time-reversal-invariant Weyl semimetals in achiral crystals require at least four Weyl nodes, whereas the minimal number of Weyl nodes in a chiral crystal is two. In achiral crystals, time-reversal symmetry maps a Weyl node of given chirality at $\mathbf{k} \neq \mathbf{k}_0$ to another Weyl node of identical chirality at $-\mathbf{k}$. This enforces a net zero chiral charge constraint in the Brillouin zone (BZ), ne-

cessitating at least four Weyl nodes [43]. In contrast, chiral crystals—lacking such constraints on Weyl nodes location—can host Weyl nodes exclusively at TRIM, allowing the minimal number of nodes to be two.

With finite carrier density, Weyl semimetals exhibit disconnected bulk Fermi surfaces (FSs), each surrounds a Weyl node. Figure 1(a) shows that the inversion-symmetric Weyl semimetal exhibits Weyl node being surrounded by a single Fermi surface. Here, the spin states at \mathbf{k} and $-\mathbf{k}$ can become parallel at the poles of the Fermi surface, leading to four nodal nodes in the spin-singlet zero-momentum internode SC state [44–47]. Although a fully gapped SC phase can be realized in the intra-node Fulde-Ferrell-Larkin-Ovchinnikov pairing at finite momentum, the absence of symmetry to relate the paired states precludes a weak-coupling superconducting instability [45]. In contrast, for time-reversal symmetric Weyl semimetal in achiral crystal (in Fig. 1(b)), each Fermi pocket is spin-polarized, each Fermi pocket is spin-polarized, potentially facilitating fully gapped internode SC pairing [43, 48].

Compared to Weyl semimetals in achiral crystals with either inversion or time-reversal symmetry, chiral Weyl semimetals exhibit distinct FS configurations and spin textures. In chiral crystals, multiple FSs (two in a two-band model) can surround the same Weyl node at TRIM, unlike the single-FS-per-node configuration in achiral systems. As shown in Fig. 1(c), these FSs are split by spin-orbit coupling and acquire nontrivial Berry phases from radial spin textures. This radial spin texture, characterized by parallel spin-momentum locking, where the spin is isotropically locked parallel to the electron’s linear momentum [49], is confirmed by spin- and angle-

FIG. 1. (Color online)(a)-(c) Fermi surface (FS) spin textures around Weyl nodes in the $k_y = 0$ plane and corresponding superconducting pairing states. Arrows indicate the spin components ($\langle\sigma_x\rangle$, $\langle\sigma_z\rangle$) for electron states on FSs. (a) Inversion-symmetric Weyl semimetal in achiral crystal: Cooper pairs form through zero-momentum internode pairing with nodal points (marked by crossed circles) occurring where the spins are maximally antiparallel. (b) Time-reversal symmetric Weyl semimetal in achiral crystal: spin-polarized FSs around Weyl nodes at Q_1 (Q_2) and $-Q_1$ ($-Q_2$) enable antiparallel spin partners for gapped zero momentum internode pairing. (c) Chiral topological semimetal in chiral crystals: Parallel spin-momentum locking on FSs enable gapped zero-momentum intranode pairing. The red line denotes the s_{\pm} -wave pairing nodal surface separating two Fermi surfaces, realizing first-order topological SC. (d) Band dispersion for a two-band chiral crystal model (Eq. 2).

resolved photoemission spectroscopy experiment very recently (Ref. [50]). The separation of FSs creates a large topological non-trivial energy window, leading to helicoid-arc surface states and features intriguing optoelectronic and spintronic properties [35, 51–54]. However, the SC pairing mechanism in chiral Weyl semimetals with this unique FSs configurations and spin-textures features remains an open question.

The band topology of a gapped odd-parity SC is determined by the relative configuration of FSs and SC pairing surfaces. Chiral topological semimetals feature multiple FSs with parallel spin-momentum locking. It has been proven that an odd number of FSs enclosing TRIM with

FIG. 2. (Color online)(a) Phase diagram showing topological s_{\pm} -wave SC (red color region), $s_{\pm} + d + id$ -wave SC (blue color regime) and topological trivial $s_{\pm} + d + id$ -wave SC regime for parameters $\{t, U, V\} = \{1, 2, -2\}$. (b) The dependence of Δ_0/Δ_s (Δ_d) on μ at $\alpha = 0.6$ (along the solid line in (a)). Dashed vertical lines indicate phase boundaries. The boundary between the topological and trivial regimes is determined by the overlapping of SC nodal surface (marked by Δ_0/Δ_s) to one of the Fermi surfaces. The boundary between the s_{\pm} and $s_{\pm} + d + id$ -wave SC regime is determined by $\Delta_{dc} = 3 \times 10^{-4} meV$.

positive SC pairing leads to a TSC phase [55]. Thus, the even number of FSs in chiral topological semimetals, which carry nontrivial Berry phases, must be separated by SC pairing nodal surfaces to realize a first-order TSC phase. Recently, it has demonstrated that, rather than pairing nodal surfaces, an odd number of removable Dirac pairing nodes enclosed by disconnected FSs are essential for realizing higher-order TSCs [15]. The presence of these removable Dirac nodes guarantees the nontrivial Berry phase on FSs and prevents the continuous contraction of Fermi surfaces to a point or their pairwise annihilation without bulk gap closing.

In this work, we first consider a s_{\pm} -wave SC pairing state with a nodal surface separating the FSs of a chiral Weyl semimetal, yielding a first-order TSC. We then introduce an additional $s_{\pm} + d_{3z^2-r^2} + id_{x^2-y^2}$ (denoted as $s_{\pm} + d + id$)-wave SC pairing, which generates nodal points between FSs and stabilizes a second-order TSC. The paper is organized as follows. In Sec. II, the Weyl semimetals in chiral and achiral crystals are compared. In Sec. III, a three-dimensional Hubbard model with on-site and inter-site interactions is used to investigate the even-parity superconducting pairing instability at the mean-field level. In Sec. IV, we show the exist-

tence of a first-order time-invariant TSC phase with the presence of s_{\pm} -wave SC pairing. In Sec. V, we present a second-order TSC phases arising from $s_{\pm} + d + id$ -wave pairing. A further discussion and conclusion are presented in Sec. VI.

II. WEYL SEMIMETAL IN CHIRAL AND ACHIRAL CRYSTALS

In this section, we systematically compare the Weyl semimetals in chiral and achiral crystals, focusing on two critical distinctions: (i) the locations of Weyl nodes in momentum space which arise from symmetry constraints and (ii) the spin textures of their Fermi surfaces. Although these two features have been previously proposed for chiral topological semimetals [56], a comprehensive comparison with Weyl semimetals in achiral crystals has been lacking in the literature. More importantly, these distinctive characteristic give gapped zero-momentum intranode superconducting pairing in chiral Weyl semimetal.

(i) Symmetry Constraints and Weyl Node Locations

Consider a generic two-band Hamiltonian for a spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ system expand around the Weyl node:

$$\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{k}) = f_0(\mathbf{k}) + \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{k}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)$ with σ_i ($i = x, y, z$) being Pauli matrices operating on the spin space, $f_0(\mathbf{k})$ denotes the kinetic energy term and $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{k}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}$ represents the spin-orbit coupling (SOC) term. The eigenvalues $E_{\pm}(\mathbf{k}) = f_0 \pm |\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{k})|$ exhibit two-band crossings at Weyl nodes when $|\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{k})| = 0$.

In chiral crystals (lacking inversion or roto-inversion symmetry), time-reversal symmetry enforces $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{k}) = -\mathbf{f}(-\mathbf{k})$. Near a TRIM \mathbf{k}_0 , the SOC term must be odd function of \mathbf{k} . For linear SOC ($\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{k}) = \hat{M}\mathbf{k}$), the matrix \hat{M} satisfies $\det(\hat{M}) \neq 0$ due to the absence of roto-inversion operations (R with $\det(R) = -1$) [56, 57].

Consequently, Weyl nodes can reside exactly at TRIMs (e.g., Γ, X), as exemplified by the minimal two-band Weyl semimetal in space group P222 (No. 16):

$$\mathcal{H}_0(\mathbf{k}) = \varepsilon(\mathbf{k})\sigma_0 + \sum_{i=x,y,z} \alpha_i \sin k_i \sigma_i, \quad (2)$$

where $\varepsilon(\mathbf{k}) = -t(\cos k_x + \cos k_y + \cos k_z) - \mu$ represents the kinetic energy, and $\alpha_i \sin k_i$ ($i = x, y, z$) denotes the spin-orbit coupling strength.

In achiral crystals (e.g., with inversion or roto-inversion symmetry), $\det(\hat{M}) = 0$ due to the existence of at least one mirror or roto-inversion operation R with $\det(R) = -1$. This forces at least one SOC component (e.g., \mathbf{f}_z) to vanish or depend on higher even-order terms on k . If $\mathbf{f}_z = 0$, degenerate points form a Kramers nodal line along $k_x = k_y = 0$ rather than an isolated point, creating

a Kramers nodal line semimetal [57]. To obtain a Weyl semimetal, higher-order terms are required. We can consider $\mathbf{f}_z(\mathbf{k}) = m - \frac{1}{2}k_x^2 - \frac{1}{2}k_y^2$ with m as a mass term, arising from band inversion. The corresponding tight-binding form under the protection of inversion symmetry $\sigma_z \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{k}) \sigma_z = \mathcal{H}(-\mathbf{k})$ [44] is:

$$\mathcal{H}_I = t(\sin k_x \sigma_x + \sin k_y \sigma_y) + t_z(\cos k_z - \cos Q)\sigma_z + (2 - \cos k_x - \cos k_y)\sigma_z - \mu. \quad (3)$$

In the parameter range $0 < |\mu/t| \ll Q$, this Hamiltonian describes a time-reversal-broken Weyl semimetal with a single pair of Weyl nodes with different chiral charged located at $k_z = \pm Q$ (Fig. 1(a)). This differs fundamentally from Weyl semimetals in chiral crystals, where the Weyl nodes are constrained to TRIM.

While band inversion mechanism was first proposed for inversion-symmetric topological semimetals, it also applies to time-reversal-symmetric systems [58, 59]. To achieve nontrivial topology, additional orbital degree of freedom represented by Pauli matrices ρ_i are needed. We can consider a four-band tight-binding model

$$\mathcal{H}_t = t(\sin k_y \sigma_z \rho_x - \sin k_x \sigma_0 \rho_y) + t_z(\cos k_z - \cos Q)\sigma_0 \rho_z + (m - \cos k_x - \cos k_y)\sigma_0 \rho_z + t'_z \sin k_z \sigma_z \rho_z - \mu, \quad (4)$$

which preserves time-reversal symmetry $\mathcal{T}\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{k})\mathcal{T} = \mathcal{H}(-\mathbf{k})$ with $\mathcal{T} = -i\rho_y\sigma_0\mathcal{K}$. The term $t'_z \sin k_z \sigma_z \rho_z$ breaks the inversion symmetry and splits the pair of Dirac points at $k_z = \pm Q$ into four Weyl nodes [43].

(ii) The Fermi surface spin texture

The second distinction manifests in the Fermi surface spin texture. While both chiral and achiral Weyl semimetals host Weyl nodes with chirality, chiral Weyl semimetals exhibit a particularly direct connection between their topological properties and Fermi surface spin texture. In these systems, the topology is unambiguously manifested in the spin texture of the FS. In striking contrast, achiral Weyl semimetals with time-reversal symmetry display their topological signatures exclusively through orbital winding patterns, with no analogous expression in spin texture.

In chiral crystal, the spin-orbit coupling splits spin degeneracy everywhere except at TRIM (Fig. 1(d)), creating two time-reversal-symmetric spin-split Fermi surfaces at chemical potential μ (Fig. 1(c)). By definition, the chirality of a Weyl node is $\mathcal{C} = \text{sign}[v_x \cdot (v_y \times v_z)]$ where $v_i = \nabla_k f_i(\mathbf{k})$ (with $i = x, y, z$) denote the effective velocities [58]. This can be equivalently expressed by the determinant $\mathcal{C} = \text{sign}[\det(\hat{M})]$. In chiral crystals, the spin polarization $\mathbf{s}_{\mathbf{k}} = \langle u_{\mathbf{k}} | \boldsymbol{\sigma} | u_{\mathbf{k}} \rangle$ with the eigenvector $u_{\mathbf{k}}$ of the upper band aligned parallel to $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{k})$, yields a radial spin texture characterized by parallel spin-momentum locking. This spin texture is recently observed by spin- and angle-resolved photoemission spectroscopy experiment [50]. Thus, the spin polarization $\mathbf{s}_{\mathbf{k}}$, which parallel

to a unit vector $\mathbf{f}(k)/|\mathbf{f}(k)|$, sweeps out the unit sphere S^2 on a Fermi surface enclosing the Weyl node. This configuration yields a nontrivial Chern number for the two-band model, $\mathcal{C} = -\text{sign}(k)\text{sign}[\mathbf{s}(k,0,0) \times (\mathbf{s}_{(0,k,0)} \cdot \mathbf{s}_{(0,0,k)})]$, corresponding to electronic topological chirality [56].

In achiral crystals, while inversion-symmetric Weyl semimetals do exhibit spin texture configurations on FSs enclosing Weyl nodes (Fig. 1(a)), the situation differs markedly in time-reversal-symmetric systems. Here, the FSs show spin polarization with antiparallel orientations at $\pm k_z$ (Fig. 1(b)), while the nontrivial topology fundamentally stems from orbital texture configurations.

III. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TOPOLOGICAL SUPERCONDUCTIVITY AND FERMI SURFACE CONFIGURATION

As established in the previous section, the Fermi surfaces in chiral topological semimetals exhibit opposite radial spin textures around TRIM. This unique feature naturally favors spin-singlet pairing, which we focus on in our analysis. On a cubic lattice, the possible pairing symmetries are classified according to the irreducible representations of the O_h group [60].

The s -wave pairing transforms under the A_{1g} representation. Of particular interest is the anisotropic s_{\pm} -wave pairing, where the superconducting gap changes sign between Fermi surfaces with opposite Chern numbers. This sign reversal is a key ingredient for realizing topological superconductivity, as it can induce nontrivial band topology in the superconducting state. Such sign reversal between the superconducting gaps on different Fermi surfaces can be achieved through the interplay of Coulomb repulsion and attractive interactions (e.g., phonon-mediated pairing), requiring careful tuning of their relative strengths [43].

Beyond s -wave pairings, the even-parity local pairing channel also include d -wave components, notably the doubly-degenerate ($d_{3z^2-r^2}, d_{x^2-y^2}$)-wave pairing belonging to the E_g representation. In principle, a small lattice distortion could stabilize the coexistence of s -wave and d -wave superconductivity. A similar mechanism has been proposed in three-dimensional Luttinger semimetals [61], where strain tunes the competition between different pairing channels. In the following, we investigate a scenario s_{\pm} -wave coexists with a $d + id$ -wave pairing state.

To study superconductivity, we introduce short-range density-density interactions, including on-site (U) and nearest-neighbor (W) interactions from the extended Hubbard model in cubic lattice. The interaction Hamiltonian is

$$\hat{H}_{\text{int}} = -U \sum_i n_{i\uparrow} n_{i\downarrow} - W \sum_{\langle ij \rangle, \sigma} n_{i\sigma} n_{j\sigma} \quad (5)$$

where $n_{i\sigma}$ is the density operator for spin σ at site i . On the Nambu basis $\Psi_{\mathbf{k}}^T = (c_{\mathbf{k}\uparrow}, c_{\mathbf{k}\downarrow}, -c_{-\mathbf{k}\downarrow}^\dagger, c_{-\mathbf{k}\uparrow}^\dagger)$, the Bogoliubov-de Gennes (BdG) Hamiltonian is $H_{\text{BdG}} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \mathcal{H}_{\text{BdG}}(\mathbf{k}) \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}$, where

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{BdG}}(\mathbf{k}) = \varepsilon(\mathbf{k})\tau_z\sigma_0 + \alpha\tau_z(\sin k_x\sigma_x + \sin k_y\sigma_y + \sin k_z\sigma_z) - \Delta(\mathbf{k})\tau_x, \quad (6)$$

where τ_i and σ_i are Pauli matrices acting in particle-hole and spin spaces, respectively. And $\varepsilon(\mathbf{k}) = -t(\cos k_x + \cos k_y + \cos k_z) - \mu$. The superconducting order parameter is expressed as

$$\Delta(\mathbf{k}) = \Delta_0 + \Delta_s\eta_s(\mathbf{k}) + \Delta_d\eta_d(\mathbf{k}). \quad (7)$$

Here, Δ_0 , Δ_s , and Δ_d represent onsite s -, extended s - and $d + id$ -wave SC respectively. The form factors $\eta_s(\mathbf{k}) = \sum_{i=x,y,z} \cos k_i$ and $\eta_d(\mathbf{k}) = (\cos k_z - \frac{1}{2} \cos k_x - \frac{1}{2} \cos k_y) + i\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}(\cos k_x - \cos k_y)$ encode the momentum dependence of the pairing potentials.

Following the standard BCS theory, the j th-channel pairing amplitude Δ_j are determined self-consistently through the gap equations

$$\Delta_j(\mathbf{k}) = - \sum_{\mathbf{k}'} V_j(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}') \langle c_{\mathbf{k}'\uparrow} c_{-\mathbf{k}'\downarrow} \rangle. \quad (8)$$

where $V_j(\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}')$ denotes the interaction strength for the j -th pairing channel ($j = 0, s, d$) with $V_0 = U$, $V_s = V_d = W$.

The pair correlations are computed from the Bogoliubov amplitudes as

$$\langle c_{\mathbf{k}\sigma} c_{-\mathbf{k}\sigma'} \rangle = u_{\sigma,1}(\mathbf{k})v_{\sigma',1}^*(\mathbf{k}) + u_{\sigma,2}(\mathbf{k})v_{\sigma',2}^*(\mathbf{k}). \quad (9)$$

These amplitudes are determined by the BdG equation $\mathcal{H}_{\text{BdG}}(\mathbf{k})\chi_{\mathbf{k},l} = E_{\mathbf{k},l}\chi_{\mathbf{k},l}$, where the BdG Hamiltonian is Eq. 6, $E_{\mathbf{k},l}$ with $l = \{1, 2\}$ refer to the two positive eigenenergies, and the corresponding eigenstates $\chi_{\mathbf{k},l} = [u_{\uparrow,l}(\mathbf{k}), u_{\downarrow,l}(\mathbf{k}), v_{\uparrow,l}(\mathbf{k}), v_{\downarrow,l}(\mathbf{k})]^T$.

We numerically solve the gap equations for a range of chemical potentials μ and the spin-orbit coupling strength α . The hopping amplitude t is set as the energy unit. The self-consistent calculations reveal the dominance of s_{\pm} -wave pairing in certain parameter ranges, while a coexistence of s_{\pm} - and $d + id$ -wave pairings emerges in others. These results are summarized in the phase diagram presented in Fig. 2, which highlights the competition between different superconducting phases.

IV. FIRST-ORDER TSC

In this section, we first focus on the regime with s -wave SC pairing, in which the $d + id$ -wave SC pairing is small and can be neglect. Since the normal part and

FIG. 3. First-order topological superconducting phases. Upper panels: Configurations of Fermi surfaces (blue/orange) and pairing nodal surface (green) for (a) closed and (b) open Fermi surfaces. Lower panel: Bogoliubov-de Gennes spectra for slab geometries with open-boundary condition only along x . Parameters: $t = 1$, $\alpha = 0.6$; (a) $\Delta_0 = -1.8$, $\Delta_s = 1$ and $\mu = -2$; (b) $\Delta_0 = -0.01$, $\Delta_s = 0.46$, $\mu = -0.3$.

the s -wave pairing part of the Hamiltonian respect time-reversal symmetry (TRS), the BdG Hamiltonian preserves time-reversal symmetry

$$\mathcal{T}\mathcal{H}_{\text{BdG}}(-\mathbf{k})\mathcal{T} = \mathcal{H}_{\text{BdG}}(\mathbf{k}) \quad (10)$$

associated with the operator $\mathcal{T} = i\tau_0\sigma_y\mathcal{K}$. Also, this model satisfies the particle-hole symmetry $\Xi\mathcal{H}_{\text{BdG}}(\mathbf{k})\Xi^{-1} = -\mathcal{H}_{\text{BdG}}(-\mathbf{k})$ with the operator $\Xi = \tau_y\sigma_y\mathcal{K}$. Thus, the system belongs to the symmetry class DIII in 3D, which mathematically classified by an integer invariant \mathbb{Z} [62]. They are different from TSC in 2D, which is classified by a \mathbb{Z}_2 . More importantly, this allows the appearance of a TSC phase with a large topological number.

It has been demonstrated that an odd-parity pairing gapped superconductor is a first-order TSC if the Fermi surface encloses an odd number of TRIMs in the Brillouin zone [55]. It is easy to see the effective odd-parity pairing from a basis transformation [63], after which the BdG Hamiltonian can be decoupled into two independent parts $\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{k}) = \mathcal{H}_+(\mathbf{k}) + \mathcal{H}_-(\mathbf{k})$

$$\mathcal{H}_{\pm}(\mathbf{k}) = \begin{pmatrix} |\varepsilon(\mathbf{k})| \pm \alpha(\mathbf{k}) & \Delta_{\pm}(\mathbf{k}) \\ \Delta_{\pm}^*(\mathbf{k}) & -|\varepsilon(\mathbf{k})| \mp \alpha(\mathbf{k}) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (11)$$

where $\Delta_{\pm}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{(\Delta_0 + \Delta_s\eta_s(\mathbf{k}))(\sin k_x \pm i \sin k_y)}{\sqrt{\sin^2 k_x + \sin^2 k_y}}$ and $\alpha(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{\Delta_0 \pm \Delta_s\eta_s(\mathbf{k})}{\sqrt{\sin^2 k_x + \sin^2 k_y + \sin^2 k_z}}$.

In the presence of spin-orbit coupling, the number of normal state FSs is determined by the energy spectra of $\mathcal{H}_-(\mathbf{k})$, since the energy spectra $\mathcal{H}_+(\mathbf{k})$ are always gapped. The FS number must be even due to the time-reversal symmetry. In particular, when $|\varepsilon(\mathbf{k})| - \alpha(\mathbf{k}) = 0$ have solutions, we can see that the normal state of a superconductor has two FSs. Although the $\alpha(\mathbf{k})$ has a different form from the general 2D model with Rashba and Dresselhaus spin-orbit couplings [24], it only changes the shape of Fermi surfaces.

In previous sections, we have demonstrated that Weyl nodes located at TRIM in chiral crystals can be surrounded by multiple Fermi surfaces. When the chemical potential μ is appropriately tuned, a closed Fermi surface can transition to an open shape as it expands toward the Brillouin zone boundary. This contrasts with achiral crystals, where a closed FS typically encloses a Weyl node away from TRIM. Although the FS in achiral crystals can expand anisotropically with chemical potential tuning, open Fermi surfaces rarely form because the FSs around different Weyl nodes tend to merge with each other before reaching the Brillouin zone boundary.

The corresponding pairing nodal surface (PNS), defined by $\Delta_s(\mathbf{k}) = 0$ always separates two regions where Δ_s has opposite signs. Indeed, according to $\cos k_x + \cos k_y + \cos k_z = -\Delta_0/\Delta_s$, the PNS in three dimensions can form either closed or open surfaces, determined by the sign of Δ_0 .

For comparison, we first look at the case with closed FSs, where the dominant superconducting pairing instability is not favored. A closed PNS must lie between two disconnected FSs to ensure opposite SC gap signs, a key feature of a topological superconductor phase. The surface states of BdG Hamiltonian exhibit a Majorana cone at the $(k_y, k_z) = (0, 0)$ point, as can be seen in Fig. 3(a). According to the bulk-edge correspondence, the number of Majorana cones matches the winding number. In the weak-pairing limit, we can use a formula [64]

$$\nu = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \text{sgn}(\Delta_i) C_i, \quad (12)$$

where $\text{sgn}(\Delta_i)$ denotes the sign of pairing on the i th FS and C_i denotes the first Chern number. The signs of pairing on the two FS are opposite, characterizing a first-order TSC phase with $\nu = 1$.

Let us look at the 3D FSs in the open shape in the first BZ, contrasting with the 2D case where FSs are closed and centered at the corner of FS, which is in a close form. Now we can see that two open FSs are separated by an open PNS without any crossings as shown in Fig. 3(b). The appearance of open FSs is a natural result of a spin-orbit coupling with three components, which splits FS in three dimensions.

For the open FS case, we analyze the topology of the gapped superconductor in a space of projectors.

FIG. 4. (Color online) Second-order topological superconducting phase. (a) Configuration of Fermi surface (blue/orange) and pairing nodal lines (black lines satisfying $\Delta_0 + \Delta_s \eta_s = 0$ and $\Delta_d \eta_d = 0$.) (b) Energy spectrum of a cylindrical sample (open boundaries in x, y) showing chiral Majorana hinge modes crossing at $k_z = 0$ and $k_z = \pi$. Chiral Majorana hinge mode along z direction. (c,d) The probability density profiles of four Majorana hinge states and the eigenvalues of the BdG Hamiltonian around zero energy (red points of the inset) at (c) $k_z = 0$ and (d) $k_z = \pi$. The parameters are $\mu = -0.65$, $\alpha = 0.6$, $\Delta_0 = -0.03$, $\Delta_s = 0.4$, $\Delta_d = 0.009$.

The projection operator for occupied state is defined as $P_{\mathbf{k}} = \sum_{n \in \text{filled}} |u_{n\mathbf{k}}\rangle \langle u_{n\mathbf{k}}|$ with $|u_{n\mathbf{k}}\rangle$ is the n -th Bloch wave function at \mathbf{k} . In the presence of chiral symmetry, $Q_{\mathbf{k}} = 2P_{\mathbf{k}} - 1$ can be further brought into an off-diagonal form $Q_{\mathbf{k}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & q_{\mathbf{k}} \\ q_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. The winding number can be written as [65]

$$\nu = \frac{1}{24\pi^2} \int_{T^3} d^3\mathbf{k} \epsilon^{ijk} \text{Tr} \left[q_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \partial_i q_{\mathbf{k}} q_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \partial_j q_{\mathbf{k}} q_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \partial_k q_{\mathbf{k}} \right], \quad (13)$$

where the integral is over the first Brillouin zone T^3 .

In the TSC phase featuring open FSs and a open PNS, we obtain a winding number of $\nu = -2$. Our mean-field calculations confirm the dominant superconducting pairing instability corresponding to this s_{\pm} -wave pairing nodal surface with opened shape. The corresponding surface state of BdG Hamiltonian exhibits two Majorana surface cones at $(k_y, k_z) = (\pi, 0)$ and $(k_y, k_z) = (0, \pi)$ points. This $\nu = -2$ phase is absent in systems with Rashba and Dresselhaus spin-orbit coupling, which have only two components.

V. SECOND-ORDER TSC

In the section, we investigate the $s_{\pm} + d + id$ wave SC pairing regime. As evident from Fig. 2(b), the amplitude of the $d_{3z^2-r^2} + id_{x^2-y^2}$ -wave SC pairing is very low, two orders of magnitude lower than the s_{\pm} -wave component in this mixed pairing state. Consequently, the $d_{3z^2-r^2}$

has minimal influence on the SC nodal surface. However, the presence of id -wave SC breaks the time-reversal symmetry. According to the symmetry classification [62], the 3D superconductor lacking TRS belongs to class D. In this case, the first-order TSC phase becomes trivial, and the helical edge states are gapped out due to TRS breaking.

Notably, the $id_{x^2-y^2}$ -wave SC order modifies the nodal structure by shrinking the pairing nodal surface into four pairing nodal lines along the $k_x = \pm k_y$ direction. These pairing nodal lines occur at generic momentum away from TRIMs, making them removable. The presence of such removable pairing nodal lines indicates that the two FSs cannot be continuously contracted to a point without closing the bulk gap. In addition, the FS with parallel spin-momentum locking has nontrivial topology. These two conditions enable the emergence of a second-order TSC phase in this system.

The configuration of FSs and pairing nodal surfaces are shown in Fig. 4(a). In the first-order TSC phase without id -wave SC, we have found two Dirac cones on (100) surface, crossing at $(k_y, k_z) = (0, \pi)$ and $(k_y, k_z) = (\pi, 0)$ respectively. When the id -wave SC is turned on, we can expect the pairing gaps of the Dirac cones to have sign reversal at two momenta simultaneously. Figure 4(b) shows that two pairs of chiral Majorana hinge modes cross at $k_z = 0$ and $k_z = \pi$ in the energy spectrum of cylinder sample with open boundary condition in x and y directions. Interestingly, these edge states are isolated from the bulk bands. The spatial profile of the eigenvalues near zero energy confirms the localization of the Majorana hinge modes for $k_z = 0$ and $k_z = \pi$ in Figs. 4(c) and (d) respectively. The emergence of four non-degenerate Majorana modes - one at each hinge - provides unambiguous evidence of time-reversal symmetry breaking in our system.

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this work, we show that both first- and second-order topological superconducting phases can emerge in a chiral topological semimetal. Unlike Weyl semimetals in achiral crystals, chiral topological semimetals are protected by chiral little group symmetry, leading to Weyl nodes located at time-reversal invariant momenta. These Weyl nodes are enclosing by Fermi surfaces with radial spin textures, characterized by parallel spin-momentum locking. These unique characteristics particularly favor zero-momentum intranode spin-singlet superconducting pairing. Mean field calculation finds s_{\pm} -wave and $s_{\pm} + d + id$ -wave pairing superconductivity phases. In the presence of s_{\pm} -wave pairing, a first-order TSC phase with $\nu = -2$ emerges naturally from the open Fermi surfaces centered at time-reversal invariant momenta. In the presence of $s_{\pm} + d + id$ -wave SC, a second-order TSC phase

for open FSs has chiral Majorana hinge modes crossing at two momenta.

In the above calculations, we use a two-band model in a space group 16 to show the existence of TSC phases in chiral topological semimetal with Weyl nodes. However, our results can be expected to generalize to other chiral crystal materials in cubic lattice with multiple band crossing points, especially RhGe and AuBe in space group 198 which exhibits superconductivity [28, 66–69]. Actually, the two features discussed in section II also exist in other chiral topological semimetals. Most importantly, multiple band crossings occur at specific time-reversal invariant momenta. Although the increasing number of Fermi surface creates a complicated configuration, those Fermi surfaces with distinct Chern numbers near the TRIM at the Brillouin zone center and Brillouin zone corners can still be separated by a pairing nodal surface. For example, in space group 198 chiral topological semimetal, the Fermi surfaces around the Γ and R points can be separated by a s_{\pm} -wave pairing nodal surface. Furthermore, the Fermi surface spin textures in other chiral topological semimetals can be more complicated. Although on-site spin-orbital entanglement and the mixing of additional basis states in nonsymmorphic cubic crystals can lead to the vanishing of radial spin-momentum locking when closer to the nodal point [49], chiral cubic symmetry enforces perfectly radial spin texture with linear momentum dependence on FSs far enough from the nodal point such that bands are only weakly spin-split [50, 70–72]. More importantly, the Chern numbers associated with these Fermi surfaces have been confirmed by experiments [33–39]. Actually, tight-binding model calculation and mean-field analysis have shown the existence of first-order TSC phase with large topological number in chiral topological semimetal with s_{\pm} SC pairing [29]. This shows that the zero-momentum intranode SC pairing can be generalized to chiral topological semimetal in cubic lattice with multiple band crossing.

Our analysis of the s_{\pm} -wave and $d+id$ -wave pairing coexistence is restricted to cases where the s_{\pm} component dominates over the $d+id$ component. However, when the $d+id$ -wave pairing strength becomes comparable to or exceeds that of the s_{\pm} -wave component, the system transitions into a nodal superconducting state. Nevertheless, as demonstrated in the analysis of chiral topological semimetal with multiple band crossing [31], such nodal superconductors may also exhibit topological properties.

Our study extends the topological superconductivity beyond the Rashba spin-orbit coupling physics. In the past decades, the connection between Rashba spin-orbit coupling and Dirac physics in topological materials has been well studied. The spin-momentum locking is admitted as a central ingredient giving rise to remarkable topological properties. However, in recent years, condensed matter physics has found new spin polarization behaviors

in Fermi surfaces. For example, in recent studies, the spin texture of the collinear and noncollinear antiferromagnetism have been linked to topological superconductivity [73]. We expect the novel spin-momentum locking in Fermi surfaces could give rise to a variety of exotic physics in TSC.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank Zhongbo Yan for helpful discussions. This work is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 12104099 and No. 12274095) and Guangzhou Science and Technology Program (Grant No. 2024A04J0272)

-
- [1] N. Read and D. Green, Paired states of fermions in two dimensions with breaking of parity and time-reversal symmetries and the fractional quantum hall effect, *Physical Review B* **61**, 10267 (2000).
 - [2] A. Y. Kitaev, Unpaired majorana fermions in quantum wires, *Physics-uspekhi* **44**, 131 (2001).
 - [3] J. Alicea, New directions in the pursuit of majorana fermions in solid state systems, *Reports on progress in physics* **75**, 076501 (2012).
 - [4] C. Beenakker, Search for majorana fermions in superconductors, *Annual Review of Condensed Matter Physics* **4**, 113 (2013).
 - [5] S. R. Elliott and M. Franz, *Colloquium* : Majorana fermions in nuclear, particle, and solid-state physics, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **87**, 137 (2015).
 - [6] M. Sato and Y. Ando, Topological superconductors: a review, *Reports on Progress in Physics* **80**, 076501 (2017).
 - [7] T. D. Stanescu and S. Tewari, Majorana fermions in semiconductor nanowires: fundamentals, modeling, and experiment, *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* **25**, 233201 (2013).
 - [8] J. Langbehn, Y. Peng, L. Trifunovic, F. von Oppen, and P. W. Brouwer, Reflection-symmetric second-order topological insulators and superconductors, *Physical review letters* **119**, 246401 (2017).
 - [9] E. Khalaf, Higher-order topological insulators and superconductors protected by inversion symmetry, *Physical Review B* **97**, 205136 (2018).
 - [10] M. Geier, L. Trifunovic, M. Hoskam, and P. W. Brouwer, Second-order topological insulators and superconductors with an order-two crystalline symmetry, *Physical Review B* **97**, 205135 (2018).
 - [11] X. Zhu, Tunable majorana corner states in a two-dimensional second-order topological superconductor induced by magnetic fields, *Physical Review B* **97**, 205134 (2018).
 - [12] Z. Yan, F. Song, and Z. Wang, Majorana corner modes in a high-temperature platform, *Physical review letters* **121**, 096803 (2018).
 - [13] Q. Wang, C.-C. Liu, Y.-M. Lu, and F. Zhang, High-temperature majorana corner states, *Physical review letters* **121**, 186801 (2018).

- [14] Y. Wang, M. Lin, and T. L. Hughes, Weak-pairing higher order topological superconductors, *Physical Review B* **98**, 165144 (2018).
- [15] Z. Yan, Higher-order topological odd-parity superconductors, *Physical review letters* **123**, 177001 (2019).
- [16] T. Liu, J. J. He, F. Nori, *et al.*, Majorana corner states in a two-dimensional magnetic topological insulator on a high-temperature superconductor, *Physical Review B* **98**, 245413 (2018).
- [17] R.-X. Zhang, W. S. Cole, X. Wu, and S. DasSarma, Higher-order topology and nodal topological superconductivity in fe (se, te) heterostructures, *Physical review letters* **123**, 167001 (2019).
- [18] X.-H. Pan, K.-J. Yang, L. Chen, G. Xu, C.-X. Liu, and X. Liu, Lattice-symmetry-assisted second-order topological superconductors and majorana patterns, *Physical review letters* **123**, 156801 (2019).
- [19] X. Zhu, Second-order topological superconductors with mixed pairing, *Physical Review Letters* **122**, 236401 (2019).
- [20] Y.-T. Hsu, W. S. Cole, R.-X. Zhang, and J. D. Sau, Inversion-protected higher-order topological superconductivity in monolayer wte 2, *Physical Review Letters* **125**, 097001 (2020).
- [21] Z. Wu, Z. Yan, and W. Huang, Higher-order topological superconductivity: Possible realization in fermi gases and sr 2 ruo 4, *Physical Review B* **99**, 020508(R) (2019).
- [22] Y. Volpez, D. Loss, and J. Klinovaja, Second-order topological superconductivity in π -junction rashba layers, *Physical review letters* **122**, 126402 (2019).
- [23] Y.-J. Wu, J. Hou, Y.-M. Li, X.-W. Luo, X. Shi, and C. Zhang, In-plane zeeman-field-induced majorana corner and hinge modes in an s-wave superconductor heterostructure, *Physical Review Letters* **124**, 227001 (2020).
- [24] M. Kheirkhah, Z. Yan, Y. Nagai, and F. Marsiglio, First-and second-order topological superconductivity and temperature-driven topological phase transitions in the extended hubbard model with spin-orbit coupling, *Physical Review Letters* **125**, 017001 (2020).
- [25] S. Qin, C. Fang, F.-C. Zhang, and J. Hu, Topological superconductivity in an extended s-wave superconductor and its implication to iron-based superconductors, *Physical Review X* **12**, 011030 (2022).
- [26] X. Wu, W. A. Benalcazar, Y. Li, R. Thomale, C.-X. Liu, and J. Hu, Boundary-obstructed topological high-t c superconductivity in iron pnictides, *Physical Review X* **10**, 041014 (2020).
- [27] A. Tsvyashchenko, V. Sidorov, A. Petrova, L. Fomicheva, I. Zibrov, and V. Dmitrienko, Superconductivity and magnetism in noncentrosymmetric rhge, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* **686**, 431 (2016).
- [28] D. Salamatin, A. Tsvyashchenko, A. Salamatin, A. Velichkov, M. Magnitskaya, N. Chtchelkatchev, V. Sidorov, L. Fomicheva, M. Mikhin, M. Kozin, *et al.*, Hyperfine field studies of the high-pressure phase of non-centrosymmetric superconductor rhge (b20) doped with hafnium, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* **850**, 156601 (2021).
- [29] Y. Huang and S.-K. Jian, Three-dimensional time reversal invariant topological superconductivity in doped chiral topological semimetals, *Physical Review B* **103**, L161113 (2021).
- [30] C. Lee, C. Yoon, T. Kim, S. B. Chung, and H. Min, Topological multiband s-wave superconductivity in coupled multifold fermions, *Physical Review B* **104**, L241115 (2021).
- [31] S. Mardanya, M. Kargarian, R. Verma, T.-R. Chang, S. Chowdhury, H. Lin, A. Bansil, A. Agarwal, and B. Singh, Unconventional superconducting pairing in a b20 multifold weyl fermion semimetal, *Physical Review Materials* **8**, L091801 (2024).
- [32] Z. S. Gao, X.-J. Gao, W.-Y. He, X. Y. Xu, T. Ng, and K. Law, Topological superconductivity in multifold fermion metals, *Quantum Frontiers* **1**, 3 (2022).
- [33] Z. Rao, H. Li, T. Zhang, S. Tian, C. Li, B. Fu, C. Tang, L. Wang, Z. Li, W. Fan, *et al.*, Observation of unconventional chiral fermions with long fermi arcs in cosi, *Nature* **567**, 496 (2019).
- [34] D. Takane, Z. Wang, S. Souma, K. Nakayama, T. Nakamura, H. Oinuma, Y. Nakata, H. Iwasawa, C. Cacho, T. Kim, *et al.*, Observation of chiral fermions with a large topological charge and associated fermi-arc surface states in cosi, *Physical review letters* **122**, 076402 (2019).
- [35] D. S. Sanchez, I. Belopolski, T. A. Cochran, X. Xu, J.-X. Yin, G. Chang, W. Xie, K. Manna, V. Süß, C.-Y. Huang, *et al.*, Topological chiral crystals with helicoid-arc quantum states, *Nature* **567**, 500 (2019).
- [36] N. B. Schröter, D. Pei, M. G. Vergniory, Y. Sun, K. Manna, F. De Juan, J. A. Krieger, V. Süß, M. Schmidt, P. Dudin, *et al.*, Chiral topological semimetal with multifold band crossings and long fermi arcs, *Nature Physics* **15**, 759 (2019).
- [37] B. Q. Lv, Z.-L. Feng, J.-Z. Zhao, N. F. Q. Yuan, A. Zong, K. F. Luo, R. Yu, Y.-B. Huang, V. N. Strocov, A. Chikina, *et al.*, Observation of multiple types of topological fermions in pdbise, *Physical Review B* **99**, 241104(R) (2019).
- [38] M. Yao, K. Manna, Q. Yang, A. Fedorov, V. Voroshnin, B. V. Schwarze, J. Hornung, S. Chattopadhyay, Z. Sun, S. N. Guin, *et al.*, Observation of giant spin-split fermi-arc with maximal chern number in the chiral topological semimetal ptga, *Nature Communications* **11**, 2033 (2020).
- [39] N. B. Schröter, S. Stolz, K. Manna, F. De Juan, M. G. Vergniory, J. A. Krieger, D. Pei, T. Schmitt, P. Dudin, T. K. Kim, *et al.*, Observation and control of maximal chern numbers in a chiral topological semimetal, *Science* **369**, 179 (2020).
- [40] B. Bradlyn, J. Cano, Z. Wang, M. Vergniory, C. Felser, R. J. Cava, and B. A. Bernevig, Beyond dirac and weyl fermions: Unconventional quasiparticles in conventional crystals, *Science* **353**, aaf5037 (2016).
- [41] G. Chang, S.-Y. Xu, B. J. Wieder, D. S. Sanchez, S.-M. Huang, I. Belopolski, T.-R. Chang, S. Zhang, A. Bansil, H. Lin, *et al.*, Unconventional chiral fermions and large topological fermi arcs in rhsi, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **119**, 206401 (2017).
- [42] P. Tang, Q. Zhou, and S.-C. Zhang, Multiple types of topological fermions in transition metal silicides, *Physical review letters* **119**, 206402 (2017).
- [43] P. Hosur, X. Dai, Z. Fang, and X.-L. Qi, Time-reversal-invariant topological superconductivity in doped weyl semimetals, *Physical Review B* **90**, 045130 (2014).
- [44] G. Y. Cho, J. H. Bardarson, Y.-M. Lu, and J. E. Moore, Superconductivity of doped weyl semimetals: Finite-momentum pairing and electronic analog of the 3 he-a

- phase, *Physical Review B—Condensed Matter and Materials Physics* **86**, 214514 (2012).
- [45] G. Bednik, A. Zyuzin, and A. Burkov, Superconductivity in weyl metals, *Physical Review B* **92**, 035153 (2015).
- [46] T. Zhou, Y. Gao, and Z. D. Wang, Superconductivity in doped inversion-symmetric weyl semimetals, *Phys. Rev. B* **93**, 094517 (2016).
- [47] T. Zhou, Y. Gao, and Z. D. Wang, Resolving different pairing states in weyl superconductors through the single-particle spectrum, *Phys. Rev. B* **98**, 024515 (2018).
- [48] X. Bai, W. LiMing, and T. Zhou, Superconductivity in weyl semimetals with time reversal symmetry, *New Journal of Physics* **27**, 013003 (2025).
- [49] M. Lin, I. Robredo, N. B. M. Schröter, C. Felser, M. G. Vergniory, and B. Bradlyn, Spin-momentum locking from topological quantum chemistry: Applications to multifold fermions, *Physical Review B* **106**, 245101 (2022).
- [50] J. A. Krieger, S. Stolz, I. Robredo, K. Manna, E. C. McFarlane, M. Date, B. Pal, J. Yang, E. B. Guedes, J. H. Dil, et al., Weyl spin-momentum locking in a chiral topological semimetal, *Nature communications* **15**, 3720 (2024).
- [51] D. Rees, K. Manna, B. Lu, T. Morimoto, H. Borrmann, C. Felser, J. Moore, D. H. Torchinsky, and J. Orenstein, Helicity-dependent photocurrents in the chiral weyl semimetal rhsi, *Science advances* **6**, eaba0509 (2020).
- [52] D. Dutta, B. Ghosh, B. Singh, H. Lin, A. Politano, A. Bansil, and A. Agarwal, Collective plasmonic modes in the chiral multifold fermionic material cosi, *Physical Review B* **105**, 165104 (2022).
- [53] T.-Y. Hsieh, B. B. Prasad, and G.-Y. Guo, Helicity-tunable spin hall and spin nernst effects in unconventional chiral fermion semimetals x y ($x = \text{co}$, rh ; $y = \text{si}$, ge), *Physical Review B* **106**, 165102 (2022).
- [54] Z. Ni, K. Wang, Y. Zhang, O. Pozo, B. Xu, X. Han, K. Manna, J. Paglione, C. Felser, A. G. Grushin, et al., Giant topological longitudinal circular photo-galvanic effect in the chiral multifold semimetal cosi, *Nature communications* **12**, 154 (2021).
- [55] L. Fu and E. Berg, Odd-parity topological superconductors: theory and application to $\text{Cu}_x\text{Bi}_{2-2x}\text{Se}_3$, *Physical review letters* **105**, 097001 (2010).
- [56] G. Chang, B. J. Wieder, F. Schindler, D. S. Sanchez, I. Belopolski, S.-M. Huang, B. Singh, D. Wu, T.-R. Chang, T. Neupert, et al., Topological quantum properties of chiral crystals, *Nature materials* **17**, 978 (2018).
- [57] Y.-M. Xie, X.-J. Gao, X. Y. Xu, C.-P. Zhang, J.-X. Hu, J. Z. Gao, and K. T. Law, Kramers nodal line metals, *Nature Communications* **12**, 3064 (2021).
- [58] N. P. Armitage, E. J. Mele, and A. Vishwanath, Weyl and dirac semimetals in three-dimensional solids, *Reviews of Modern Physics* **90**, 015001 (2018).
- [59] S. Murakami and S. I. Kuga, Universal phase diagrams for the quantum spin hall systems, *Physical Review B—Condensed Matter and Materials Physics* **78**, 165313 (2008).
- [60] M. Smidman, M. Salamon, H. Yuan, and D. Agterberg, Superconductivity and spin-orbit coupling in non-centrosymmetric materials: a review, *Reports on Progress in Physics* **80**, 036501 (2017).
- [61] B. Roy, S. A. A. Ghorashi, M. S. Foster, and A. H. Nevidomskyy, Topological superconductivity of spin-3/2 carriers in a three-dimensional doped luttinger semimetal, *Physical Review B* **99**, 054505 (2019).
- [62] C.-K. Chiu, J. C. Y. Teo, A. P. Schnyder, and S. Ryu, Classification of topological quantum matter with symmetries, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **88**, 035005 (2016).
- [63] See the supplemental material for effective odd-parity superconductivity model.
- [64] X.-L. Qi, T. L. Hughes, and S.-C. Zhang, Topological invariants for the fermi surface of a time-reversal-invariant superconductor, *Physical Review B* **81**, 134508 (2010).
- [65] A. P. Schnyder, S. Ryu, A. Furusaki, and A. W. W. Ludwig, Classification of topological insulators and superconductors in three spatial dimensions, *Physical Review B* **78**, 195125 (2008).
- [66] B. Matthias, Superconductivity of aube, *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids* **10**, 342 (1959).
- [67] D. J. Rebar, S. M. Birnbaum, J. Singleton, M. Khan, J. C. Ball, P. W. Adams, J. Y. Chan, D. P. Young, D. A. Browne, and J. F. DiTusa, Fermi surface, possible unconventional fermions, and unusually robust resistive critical fields in the chiral-structured superconductor aube, *Physical Review B* **99**, 094517 (2019).
- [68] R. Khasanov, R. Gupta, D. Das, A. Amon, A. Leithe-Jasper, and E. Svanidze, Multiple-gap response of type-I noncentrosymmetric beau superconductor, *Physical Review Research* **2**, 023142 (2020).
- [69] R. Khasanov, R. Gupta, D. Das, A. Leithe-Jasper, and E. Svanidze, Single-gap versus two-gap scenario: Specific heat and thermodynamic critical field of the non-centrosymmetric superconductor beau, *Physical Review B* **102**, 014514 (2020).
- [70] W. Tan, X. Jiang, Y. Li, X. Wu, J. Wang, and B. Huang, A unified understanding of diverse spin textures of kramers-weyl fermions in nonmagnetic chiral crystals, *Advanced Functional Materials* **32**, 2208023 (2022).
- [71] C. Mera Acosta, L. Yuan, G. M. Dalpian, and A. Zunger, Different shapes of spin textures as a journey through the brillouin zone, *Physical Review B* **104**, 104408 (2021).
- [72] D. Gosálbez-Martínez, A. Crepaldi, and O. V. Yazyev, Diversity of radial spin textures in chiral materials, *Physical Review B* **108**, L201114 (2023).
- [73] S. H. Lee, Y. Qian, and B.-J. Yang, Fermi surface spin texture and topological superconductivity in spin-orbit free noncollinear antiferromagnets, *Physical Review Letters* **132**, 196602 (2024).
- [74] J. Alicea, Majorana fermions in a tunable semiconductor device, *Physical Review B* **81**, 125318 (2010).

Supplemental Material

I. EFFECTIV ODD-PARITY SUPERCONDUCTIVITY MODEL

The normal state Hamiltonian with parallel spin-momentum coupling is

$$H_0 = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} (c_{\mathbf{k},\uparrow}^\dagger, c_{\mathbf{k},\downarrow}^\dagger) \begin{pmatrix} \xi_{\mathbf{k}} + \alpha_z & \alpha_x - i\alpha_y \\ \alpha_x + i\alpha_y & \xi_{\mathbf{k}} - \alpha_z \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{\mathbf{k},\uparrow} \\ c_{\mathbf{k},\downarrow} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{S-1})$$

where $\alpha_i = \alpha \sin k_i$ for $i = x, y, z$. Note that $\alpha_z = \alpha \sin k_z$ is different from the out-of-plane Zeeman field, which is used in the basis transformation mapping the spin-orbit coupling and $s + id$ -wave pairing to an effective odd-parity pairing [24] Here, for $k' = -k$, $\alpha_z(-\mathbf{k}) = -\alpha_z(\mathbf{k})$.

The even-parity superconductivity(SC) is described by

$$H_{\text{SC}} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} (\Delta_s(\mathbf{k}) + i\Delta_d(\mathbf{k})) c_{\mathbf{k},\uparrow}^\dagger c_{-\mathbf{k},\downarrow}^\dagger + h.c., \quad (\text{S-2})$$

where $\Delta_s(\mathbf{k}) = \Delta_0 + \Delta_s \eta_s(\mathbf{k})$ and $\Delta_d(\mathbf{k}) = \Delta_d \eta_d(\mathbf{k})$.

The SC part can be rewritten on the Nambu basis as

$$H_{\text{SC}} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} (c_{\mathbf{k},\uparrow}^\dagger, c_{\mathbf{k},\downarrow}^\dagger) \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -(\Delta_s(\mathbf{k}) + i\Delta_d(\mathbf{k})) \\ (\Delta_s(\mathbf{k}) + i\Delta_d(\mathbf{k})) & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{-\mathbf{k},\uparrow}^\dagger \\ c_{-\mathbf{k},\downarrow}^\dagger \end{pmatrix} + h.c. \quad (\text{S-3})$$

Following Ref. [24, 74], we can do the transformation,

$$(c_{\mathbf{k},\uparrow}^\dagger, c_{\mathbf{k},\downarrow}^\dagger) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \frac{\theta_{\mathbf{k}}}{2} & e^{-i\phi_{\mathbf{k}}} \sin \frac{\theta_{\mathbf{k}}}{2} \\ e^{-i\phi_{\mathbf{k}}} \sin \frac{\theta_{\mathbf{k}}}{2} & -\cos \frac{\theta_{\mathbf{k}}}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{\mathbf{k},+}^\dagger \\ c_{\mathbf{k},-}^\dagger \end{pmatrix} + h.c., \quad (\text{S-4})$$

where $\theta_{\mathbf{k}}$ satisfies $\cos \theta_{\mathbf{k}} = \alpha_z / \alpha_{\mathbf{k}}$ with $\alpha_{\mathbf{k}} = \sqrt{\alpha_x^2 + \alpha_y^2 + \alpha_z^2}$ and $\phi_{\mathbf{k}}$ satisfies $e^{i\phi_{\mathbf{k}}} = (\alpha_x + i\alpha_y) / \sqrt{\alpha_x^2 + \alpha_y^2}$. This is different from $\alpha_{\mathbf{k}} = \sqrt{\alpha_x^2 + \alpha_y^2}$ for Rashba spin-orbit coupling [24].

The normal part can be written in a diagonal form

$$H_0 = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} (\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}} + \alpha) c_{\mathbf{k},+}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{k},+} + (\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}} - \alpha) c_{\mathbf{k},-}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{k},-}. \quad (\text{S-5})$$

Fortunately, the superconducting part can also be written in a diagonal form

$$H_{\text{SC}} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\frac{-(\Delta_s(\mathbf{k}) + i\Delta_d(\mathbf{k}))(\alpha_x + i\alpha_y)}{\sqrt{\alpha_x^2 + \alpha_y^2}} c_{\mathbf{k},+}^\dagger c_{-\mathbf{k},+}^\dagger + h.c. \right) \\ + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\frac{-(\Delta_s(\mathbf{k}) + i\Delta_d(\mathbf{k}))(\alpha_x - i\alpha_y)}{\sqrt{\alpha_x^2 + \alpha_y^2}} c_{\mathbf{k},-}^\dagger c_{-\mathbf{k},-}^\dagger + h.c. \right). \quad (\text{S-6})$$

The Hamiltonian can be decoupled into two parts, $H = H_+ \oplus H_-$, with

$$H_+ = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k},+} c_{\mathbf{k},+}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{k},+} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\frac{(\Delta_s(\mathbf{k}) + i\Delta_d(\mathbf{k}))(\alpha_x + i\alpha_y)}{\sqrt{\alpha_x^2 + \alpha_y^2}} c_{\mathbf{k},+}^\dagger c_{-\mathbf{k},+}^\dagger + h.c. \right), \quad (\text{S-7})$$

$$H_- = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k},-} c_{\mathbf{k},-}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{k},-} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \left(\frac{(\Delta_s(\mathbf{k}) + i\Delta_d(\mathbf{k}))(\alpha_x + i\alpha_y)}{\sqrt{\alpha_x^2 - \alpha_y^2}} c_{\mathbf{k},-}^\dagger c_{-\mathbf{k},-}^\dagger + h.c. \right). \quad (\text{S-8})$$